

EFFECTS OF ASTHENIC SYNDROME-INDUCED SLEEP DISTURBANCES ON STUDENTS' QUALITY OF LIFE.

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Relevance. To study the impact of sleep disturbances caused by asthenic syndrome on students' quality of life, statistical analysis was conducted. Asthenic syndrome is the weakening of a physical and mental state that can negatively impact a student's psychological and physical health. In particular, sleep disturbances significantly affect the student's daily activities, learning process, and personal life.

Purpose. The purpose of this study is to examine how sleep disturbances caused by asthenic syndrome impact students' physical, emotional, and social well-being. It aims to explore the relationship between sleep quality and overall quality of life, including academic performance and mental health.

Research material and methods. A total of 336 respondents participated. The main group consisted of medical students, control group - students of other specialties.

The number of students in the main group was 185, which constituted 55% of the total number of examined. Those surveyed who did not study at medical universities, taken for the control group, amounted to 151, which is 45% of the total number of students.

The tested students completed the tests posted on the Google platform remotely. The tests were developed between January 2025 and February 2025.

Discussion of results.

To determine the sleep quality index, the results of the Pittsburgh Questionnaire (PSQI) were assessed in the range of 0-21 points. <5 points - good sleep quality; >6 points - poor sleep quality. Results of the main group: 8 points for 7 components; 5 points for 7 components in the control group. The sleep quality of medical university students, who make up the main group, was worse compared to students studying in other specialties.

The results obtained for the total score and sub-scales of the test of the subjective assessment scale of asthenia (MFI-20) showed that asthenia is present in both medical students and students of other specialties, but this

indicator is somewhat higher in the control group. Results according to the sub-scales -decreased activity is higher in the control group; -decreased motivation is higher in the control group; -physical asthenia is higher in the control group; -psychological asthenia is higher in the control group; However, according to the sub-scales, asthenia was absent in neither of the examined groups.

Generalized results of 2 tests: The general results of the tests show that students from the main group experienced poor sleep quality but did not show pronounced asthenia on the overall asthenia scale, with no signs of asthenia in the sub-scales. In contrast, students control group exhibited good sleep quality, with asthenia levels higher than those of the main group, though still not severe. However, no asthenia was observed in the sub-scales for either group.

Conclusion. The research results show that in the main group of students, despite poor sleep quality, the asthenic state was subjectively felt less. Students of other specialties felt tired despite having slept well. Medical students have become accustomed to high levels of stress and academic workload, resulting in them experiencing less asthenia despite improved sleep. This situation demonstrates the specifics of fatigue perception and its subjective assessment in medical university students. Students of other specialties, despite good sleep quality, had higher levels of stress and fatigue.

Literature:

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